

FEM ANALYSIS OF THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX COMPOSITE GAS CYLINDERS

P. J. Antunes¹, G. R. Dias¹, J. P. Nunes¹, F.W.J. van Hattum¹ and T. Oliveira²

¹ *Polymer Engineering Department, University of Minho
4800-058 Guimarães, Portugal*

² *AMTROL-ALFA Metalomecânica, SA,
P.O. Box 37- Brito, 4801-909 Guimarães, Portugal*

SUMMARY: Continuous glass/polypropylene (GF/PP) commingled fibre tapes were used to produce wrapped pressure gas vessels for domestic applications. The vessel structural-wall was built using a hybrid solution consisting in a very thin steel liner over-wrapped by the filament wounded GF/PP commingled fibre tape layers. FEM analysis was used to evaluate if the composite gas pressure vessel based on the hybrid solution (steel liner + glass fibre reinforced thermoplastic) is capable to withstand the pressure requirements defined in the prEN 12245 European draft standard. Finally, gas pressure vessel prototypes manufactured in industrial cycle conditions were submitted to burst pressure tests to prove that they accomplish all European standard strength requirements.

KEYWORDS: Finite element analysis, Thermoplastic matrix composite, Composite gas cylinder, Mechanical behaviour, Filament winding, Glass/Polypropylene commingled tapes

INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix composite materials are one excellent alternative to the traditional steel solutions used in the fabrication pressure gas cylinders for domestic applications. Their use in the production of pressure vessels minimizes the weight, improves the mechanical and impact behaviour and promotes handling of the cylinders [1]. Thermoplastics may also replace with advantage thermosets as matrix in composites because they present higher toughness, durability and damping properties, easier storage, possibilities of reshaping and reparability and allow increasing the production rate with much lower environmental impact (no styrene emissions and possibility of recycling) [2].

This paper presents an industrial project where finite element analysis was used to prove that was possible producing gas pressure vessels based on a hybrid solution, consisting on a steel liner wrapped with a glass fibre reinforced polypropylene (GF/PP) filament winding structure.

RAW MATERIALS AND VESSEL CHARACTERISTICS

The glass/polypropylene commingled fibre tapes (TWINTEX[®]) used to produce the composite gas vessels studied in this work were supplied by Saint-Gobain. Table 1 summarises the mechanical properties of the tapes used in the FEM analysis. The values

under the column “Calculated Values” were predicted from the manufacturer data sheets using well-know equations from the micromechanical theory of composite materials [3-6].

Table 1 – Properties of TWINTEX®

Property	Unit	Data Sheet Values	Calculated Values
Longitudinal Strength	MPa	700	-
Longitudinal Modulus	GPa	38	-
Transversal Strength	MPa	-	30
Transversal Modulus	GPa	-	1.9
Shear Strength	MPa	-	17
Shear Modulus	GPa	-	0.7
Poisson’s Ratio	-	-	0.35
Thermal conductivity	W/mK	-	0.19-0.38
Electrical resistivity	Ωm	-	2×10^{10}
Density	g/cm^3	1.75	-
Glass mass content	Wt%	75	-
Glass volume content	Vol%	50	-

The company AMTROL-ALFA produced the liner from mild steel sheets by welding two deep-formed half parts. Due to hardening different properties were determined from tensile tests in samples cut from the steel liner dome and cylinder zones. Table 2 and Figure 1 show the properties determined from those tests and used in the FEM simulations.

Table 2 – Properties of the steel liner

Property	Unit	Dome	Cylinder
Tensile Modulus	GPa	206.8	
Yield Strength	MPa	305	436
Shear Strength	MPa	176	251.6
Shear Modulus	GPa	79.2	
Tensile Strength	MPa	340	468
Hardening Modulus	MPa	127	445
Ultimate Strain	%	28.1	7.5

Figure 1 – Properties of the steel liner

A vessel having a capacity and an internal diameter of 0.02m^3 and 242mm, respectively, was considered in this study. The following laminate stacking sequence of glass/polypropylene

commingled fibres was considered: a $[\pm 30^\circ, 90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ in the cylindrical vessel zone and a non-geodesic fibre pattern in the dome.

FEM ANALYSIS

Methodology

The mechanical behaviour of the gas cylinder was predicted by finite element analysis using *Algor V13.4* and *Abaqus 6.4* FEM packages [7]. The following sequence of analysis was used:

- Linear study of the steel liner.
- Non-linear study of the steel liner (material and geometric non-linearities)
- Linear study of the composite wall (steel + GF/PP laminate)
- Non-linear study of the composite wall (steel + GF/PP laminate)

The study of the mechanical behaviour of the composite gas cylinder was based on the following theories:

- Micromechanics models to predict the composite laminae properties
- Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) to predict composite laminate properties
- Elasto-plastic behaviour of the steel liner
- Tsai-Wu failure criteria in the composite laminate
- Von-Mises stress in the steel liner
- Soderberg criterion in the analysis of the steel liner fatigue behaviour

Finite elements

Fibre orientation, thickness distribution, stacking sequence and number of layers were the parameters used to describe the laminate composite structure using shell composite linear elements. Figure 2 shows the ply stacking sequence and the material orientation angles used in the FEM simulations for the cylindrical vessel zone.

Figure 2 – Ply stacking sequence and material orientation angles in cylinder

The shell composite elements allow the introduction of the steel liner non-linear material properties in order to accurately predict the vessel burst pressure.

Simpson's integration rule (tree points through the thickness) was used to calculate the cross-sectional behaviour of the shell. Reduced integration formulation was applied for the shear components of the stiffness matrix for the other matrix terms full integration was applied. Also the element is stabilized for spurious modes, enabling a correct discrete spatial description.

In the FEM model the variation of the thickness along the vessel was taken into account in different zones as figure 3 shows.

Figure 3 – Composite vessel thickness distribution zones

As can be seen in Figure 4, the composite thickness varies along the vessel being maximum near the gas valve (dome) due to the filament winding stacking process. The increase of thickness due to the central weld line was also taken in consideration.

Figure 4 – Vessel thickness distribution

Loads and boundary conditions

In the FEA model, the composite gas cylinder was submitted to a constant and sinusoidal cycle of internal pressure in order to simulate its behaviour in service and determine the burst pressure and the fatigue behaviour. A linear variation was imposed to internal pressure (1MPa per second).

The maximum pressure value introduced for the steel liner and composite wall linear analysis was fixed in 4.75 MPa. The value of the maximum pressure was increased to 13 MPa in the composite vessel non-linear analysis to allow the prediction of the vessel burst pressure.

For the fatigue analysis a cyclic pressure ($P_{max}=3$ MPa, $P_{min}=0$ MPa, $f=0.25$ Hz) during two cycles, was applied. In order to prevent rigid body motion of the vessel during the analysis a encastre boundary condition was applied to the vessel valve. For the steel liner non-linear analysis symmetry boundary conditions were also applied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results obtained from the FEM simulations were compared with pressure requirements of the prEN 12245 standard for a vessel to withstand a working pressure of 2 MPa that are shown in Table 3.

Table 3 – Pressure requirements of prEN 12245 standard.

Property	Units	Value
Hydraulic test	MPa	3
Minimum steel liner burst pressure		4
Minimum vessel burst pressure		6.75

Steel liner non-linear analysis

Figures 5 to 8 show the strains and stresses determined in the steel liner in order to determine the burst pressure of the liner.

The figures above represent the Von Mises stress fields for the overall steel liner behaviour considering the non-linear analysis.

The obtained results demonstrated that failure occurs in steel liner dome zone as can be seen in the magnifications shown in Figures 7 and 8. The strain and stress values obtained in this analysis allow to predict that the burst pressure of the steel liner is the range [4.5, 4.75] MPa, which are values accomplishing the requirements of the prEN 12245 standard presented in Table 3.

Composite vessel linear analysis

This analysis was conducted using FEM/FEA Algor V 13.4 software using shell composite elements to verify that the vessel has a linear mechanical behaviour during the hydraulic test.

Figure 9 – Von Mises stress ($P=3$ MPa; Layer1-Steel)

The figure 9 represents the mechanical response of steel liner for the composite vessel linear analysis. The steel liner yield stress is not reached with a internal pressure equal to 3 MPa.

Figure 10 – Tsai-Wu failure criteria (layer 2) Figure 11 – Tsai-Wu failure criteria (layer 5)

The Tsai-Wu failure criterion was used to predict the failure of the glass fibre reinforced polypropylene plies. As can be seen in Figures 10 and 11, for a internal pressure of 3 MPa the thermoplastic layers are not damaged ($R>1$).

Figure 12 – Composite vessel radial deformation (magnified)

Composite vessel non-linear analysis

In order to predict the vessel burst pressure, a non-linear analysis was conducted introducing inelastic properties in the steel liner. ABAQUS 6.4 was used for this non-linear analysis using shell composite elements.

The FEM analysis predicts failure on layers 2 or 5 due to interlaminar shear when an internal pressure between 7.2 and 7.9 MPa is applied to the vessel.

Figure 17 – Plastic deformation of the steel liner ($P=7.2$ MPa; Layer1-Steel)

The plastic deformation of the steel liner for an internal pressure of 7.2 MPa (limit value for layers 2 and 5) is less than the ultimate strain and stress, which indicates that the beginning of the vessel damage is initiated by the failure of the reinforced thermoplastic layers.

The above results show that the vessel accomplishes the minimum burst pressure requirement of 6.75 MPa defined in the prEN 12245 standard.

Composite vessel resistance to pressure cycles

The fatigue behaviour of the wrapped cylinder has been evaluated for unlimited life of the steel liner (1×10^8 cycles), using the Soderberg criterion for fatigue.

$$n = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{\sigma_a}{\sigma_f}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_m}{\sigma_y}\right)} \quad (1)$$

By the Soderberg criterion if $n > 1$, unlimited life is achieved.

In the case of steel, the fatigue limit stress is a function of the yield strength and at 1×10^8 cycles (unlimited life) equals to:

$$\sigma_f = 0.504\sigma_r \quad (2)$$

The equivalent midrange stress and the stress amplitude were calculated using the Von Mises criterium, monitoring the values of stress from vessel zones where these values are maxima.

Figure 18 – Soderberg safety factor for an unlimited life (1×10^8 cycles)

The unlimited life (1×10^8 load cycles) is not achieved for the liner dome ($n < 1$), but for the 12×10^3 load cycles (required by the prEN 12245 standard) no fatigue problems will occur in the steel liner.

VESSEL PROTOTYPE PRODUCTION

Prototype composite vessels (Fig. 19) were manufactured in the conditions used in the FEM simulations using a 6 axes CNC controlled filament winding machine and submitted to hydraulic burst pressure tests. The obtained results have shown that vessel burst occurred for pressures between 8 and 11 MPa. Such results show that conservative results were obtained from FEM analysis probably because failure does not occur by interlaminar shear as simplified theories, like the netting one, demonstrate.

Figure 19 – Typical prototype vessel

CONCLUSIONS

The proposed vessel seems to adequately fulfill all the studied requirements of the prEN 12245 standard, namely:

- The FEM simulations allowed to conclude that the steel liner supports an internal pressure between 4.5 and 4.75 MPa, accomplishing the minimum required liner burst pressure ($P_{hl}=4$ MPa)

- The simulations also lead to the conclusion that the composite vessels support without damage the required hydraulic pressure ($P_h=3$ MPa)
- The simulations show that composite vessel support a minimum required burst of $P_b= 6.75$ MPa. The simulations predict failures on layers 2 or 5 at internal pressures between 7.2 and 7.9 MPa, respectively.
- FEM analysis may be assumed as a conservative estimation of the composite vessel burst because it predicted interlaminar shear failure of composite layers. In fact, higher experimental burst pressures between 8 and 11 MPa were obtained in the manufactured prototypes. This allows to conclude that interlaminar shear stresses are probably not the structural failure main cause.
- FEM analysis predicts that the steel liner by itself already passes the required fatigue test, which means that the composite vessel is structurally stable up to 12000 cycles.

REFERENCES

1. Brandt, J., Drechsler, K., Richter, H., “The Use of High-Performance Thermoplastic Composites for Structural Aerospace Applications”, *9th Int. Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM-9)*, Vol. 6, Madrid, Spain, 1993, pp. 143-150.
2. Nunes, J. P., Silva, J. F., Marques, A. T., Crainic, N., Cabral-Fonseca, S, “Production of Powder Coated Towpregs and Composites”, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, Vol. 16 (3), 2003, pp. 231-248.
3. Tsai, S.W., *Composites Design*, Think Composites, USA, 1987.
4. Jones, R.M., *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, International Student Edition, MacGraw-Hill Kogakusha Ltd, Tokyo, 1975.
5. Saarela, O., *LAMDA-Laminate Design and Analysis*, Helsinki University of Technology, Otaniemi, Finland, 1992.
6. Nunes, J. P., Bernardo, C. A., Pouzada, A. S. e Edie, D. D., “Formation and Characterisation of Carbon/Polycarbonate Towpregs and Composites”, *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 31 (17), 1997, pp 1758-1777, USA.
7. Abaqus Documentation, Version 6.4, Hibbitt, Karlsson & Sorensen Inc.